

Stochasticity at a Single Particle Level?

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In previous notes (1), we argued that stochasticity (in x and t for a fixed E energy and p momentum) may occur at a single particle level based on the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ ((1)). This invariant is also the relativistic/nonrelativistic classical action for $v=x/t$. The argument made in (1) was that a fluctuation in t of constant/ E could cancel one in x of constant/ p . We further argued one could create eigenvalue equations using id/dt and $-id/dx$ and obtain the two dimensional probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, i.e obtain a description of free particle quantum mechanics.

Experimentally, both $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ have been verified through interference patterns. Theoretically, however, ((1)) was known about 1905 and no single particle stochasticity was associated with it. In this note, we try to argue why there should be an associated stochasticity associated with ((1)) based on motion through a constant potential for a particle with rest mass and motion through a medium with an index of refraction for a photon. We in fact argue that one cannot solve certain photon problems such as one dimensional reflection/refraction without explicitly considering the stochasticity which is usually left out when describing $p_2=pn_2$ and $c_2=c/n_2$ where n_2 is the index of refraction in the second medium and p and c are values in the first medium with $n_1=1$.

We further consider $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ as arising from the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to certain constraints. The product of these two two-dimensional periodic probabilities is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which we argue must hold as seen from observers moving with constant velocity. Thus we argue that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ follows from statistical considerations alone. Given this expression (a subset of the whole picture), one may try to create a deterministic viewpoint by setting $x/t=v=constant$. This allows one to consider transformations which define E and p in terms of m_0 and v and yields the invariant $EE = pp + m_0m_0$ ($c=1$). Thus we argue that the conservation of energy equation ultimately follows from a deterministic view of the argument of a statistical probability. In other words, it is only a subset of the full picture i.e the quantum mechanical statistical one.

Motion Through a Constant Potential

Consider a particle moving through a constant potential. It has energy $pp/2m + V_0$ nonrelativistically and at first glance does not seem to undergo any changes. In such a case, one might consider dropping the potential, but physically it exists. In such a case, we suggest some kind of interactions must be occurring and that these should be stochastic as on average nothing happens to the particle. Thus it seems there may be physical motivation for some kind of stochasticity in a single particle in a constant potential.

We next consider the Klein-Gordon form:

$$(E-V_0)(E-V_0) = pp + m_0m_0 \text{ with } c=1, m_0 \text{ is rest mass and } V_0 \text{ is a constant potential } ((2))$$

This points to the Lorentz invariant: $-(E-V_0)t + px = -Et + px + V_0t$ ((3))

Here $E = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V_0$ which is considered to be stochastic. We assume V_0 is not stochastic. In other words, total energy E is associated with a kind of stochasticity and associated with the variable t . We thus suggest that there may be stochasticity in time and note that $t_2 = t_1 + \text{constant}/E$ combined with $x_2 = x_1 + \text{constant}/p$ leaves the $-Et + px$ term invariant. Thus there may be combined stochasticity in t and x .

Interface Of Two Constant Potentials With Energy Being Constant

We next consider a particle moving in the x direction in a region with a constant potential V_1 with momentum p_1 and rest mass m . An interface exists at $x=0$ in the y direction such that a different constant potential V_2 exists for $x>0$. If energy remains constant, the $-Et$ term is associated with $\text{constant}/E$ in both regions i.e. from the point of view of fluctuations in time nothing happens. From the point of view of p , momentum, an impulse occurs at the interface as p_1 becomes p_2 . In Newtonian mechanics, there would be no stochasticity associated with such a change, but $-Et + px$ suggests that stochasticity in time is also associated with stochasticity in x . Thus it seems that stochasticity changes in space i.e. the single particle re-equilibrates during the impulse hit. How does one apply a probability to such a particle? We have suggested before maximizing a spatial entropy subject to the Lagrange multiplier p with the constraint of an average x value i.e.

Maximize $P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to $i p x P(x)$ ((4))

In ((4)), the complex i is used to ensure periodicity instead of growth of the probability. ((4)) leads to $\exp(ipx)$.

The maximization result of ((4)) is: $\ln(P(x)) + 1 = ipx$.

Taking the complex conjugate of this and adding yields $\ln(P^*P) + 2 = 0$ or $P^*P = \text{constant}$ which means that the unusual two dimensional periodic probability is linked to a smooth view of motion which ignores stochasticity, but is incomplete in that it does not show the full physical information.

A new p leads to a new length $\text{constant}/p$. This length is called a wavelength and is relevant to n-slit interference experiments. Given that the particle seems to move in time without noticing any changes, we suggest it should move in space in a similar way, but p clearly changes due to the impulse. Thus there needs to be a new wavelength so that $p_1 \text{ wavelength}_1 = p_2 \text{ wavelength}_2$. Both of these are the argument of the two dimensional probability ((4)) and so with a change in wavelength, one again has similar motion (scaled) in each region.

Similarly, one may:

Maximize $P(t) \ln(P(t))$ subject to $-i E t P(t)$ ((5)) to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ ((5))

We use a minus sign so that the product: $P(t)P(x)=\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ i.e. for a fluctuation of constant/E and constant/p, the overall phase remains constant. The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, is the argument of the product of maximized time and space probabilities. Thus the deterministic Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ seems to follow from two maximum entropy subject to constraint calculations and may not be deterministic after all.

In fact, we argue that $-Et+px$ follows from probabilistic considerations and that one may then analyze $-Et+px$ (a subset of the whole picture) in a deterministic way. In particular, one may assign $v=\text{constant}=x/t$. If the form $-Et+px$ is an invariant as seen from different frames moving at a constant velocity because the probabilistic result $-Et+px=0$ must be the same in all frames (physically), one may determine the constant v frame transformation.

At this point, E and p are parameters associated with two physical processes. E may be associated with climbing up a potential hill and the p with hitting (breaking a target). E and p are not associated with v or m_0 (rest mass) yet. In the deterministic scenario, there is no probability in x or t so one may have the particle at $x=0, t=t_0$ with rest m_0 . We suggest that the rest mass is energy. As seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$, one has $x'/t'=v$ so:

$$\begin{vmatrix} f(v) & vf(v) \\ -vf(v) & f(v) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |x=0| \\ |t_0| \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} |x'| \\ |t'| \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5a))$$

The same unitary transformation should apply to (p,E) . In order to have a row vector have a unit magnitude subject to the metric $(1,-1)$ one has:

$$bf - vvf = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad f = 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{To make units agree } v \text{ should be replaced with } v/b \text{ where}$$

b has units of a velocity. (One may show from photon considerations that $v=c$.) Using this transformation, one may show that:

$$E = m_0cc / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((5b))$$

Furthermore, there exists another invariant: $EE = pp+m_0m_0$ ((5b)) ($c=1$) which represents a conservation of energy type of statement. These statements all hold in the deterministic approach applied to the argument $-Et+px$ of a stochastic probability and so do not represent the full physical picture. Nevertheless one obtains a conservation of energy equation which describes v .

Consequences of $\exp(ipx)$

In previous notes, we called $\exp(ipx)$ a built-in flux like probability. It is based on momentum p and so is expected to be linked with impulse hits, but each time such a hit occurs, a new equilibration needs to take place. For different values of p , we suggest different entropies based on Shannon's entropy and the probability $C |\cos(px)|$. Unlike Newtonian mechanics where only an impulse hit occurs, impulse interactions must be linked with the various equilibrated $\exp(ipx)$ s which act like probabilities. This applies to an n -slit experiment, where the different impulse hits

(from each slit) lead to probabilities with p having the same magnitude, but different directions. These add as they are OR probabilities even for the two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$ case, we argue.

Another interesting consequence of the x probability fluctuations associated with p and impulse hits occurs for a single photon with momentum p moving in the x direction and hitting an interface of two indices of refraction, $n_1=1$ and $n_2>n_1$ along the y axis at $x=0$. The photon may reflect or refract and at first this seems to be associated with the kind of impulse hits that occur at the interface. A certain impulse may knock the photon back into the $n_1=1$ medium with momentum $-p$ while different impulses allow it to move in the second medium with $p_2=n_2p$ and $c_2=c_1/n_2$. Again, like with the constant potential, motion through a medium with a different index of refraction n_2 may suggest various stochastic interactions. Thus the motion is smooth only on average. The same argument holds in the region with n_1 . Thus $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$ seem appropriate for this kind of situation as they are based on $-Et+px$ which describes both average motion and built-in fluctuations. In fact, this stochastic view of the motion is essential to solving the problem. As a result of the probability fluctuations in each medium, one needs a balance in space. Given that E is the same for the reflected, refracted and incident photon, $\exp(-iEt)$ may be ignored. Thus:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((6)) \text{ where } A,B,C \text{ are weights}$$

((6)) is a continuity equation based on the fluctuation probabilities associated with having a momentum. Momentum, however, suggests flux in space so one would expect A,B,C to somehow be associated with flux. Furthermore ((6)) contains two unknowns B,C if A is considered known. As argued before, one also has the equation:

$$\text{Number of incident photons} = \text{number of reflected} + \text{number of refracted} \quad ((7))$$

Writing ((7)) in terms of flux divided by speed one has:

$$\text{Flux incident photons}/c - |\text{flux reflected}|/c = \text{flux refracted} / c_2 \quad ((8))$$

((6)) shows that $B<0$ for $n_2>n_1$, thus A,B,C cannot be fluxes. Given that impulses occur in the picture associated with ((6)), one may also consider a momentum balance i.e.

$$Ap - Bp = Cp_2 \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((9))$$

One may then combine ((6)) and ((9)) to obtain: $AAp = BBp + CCp_2$. Using $E=pc$ with the same E for all photons, one has: $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ so AA, BB, CC are fluxes.

Thus the built-in probability $\exp(ipx)$ due to the stochastic motion of a single particle in a constant potential or medium with an index of refraction actually governs the probabilities of reflection/refraction (as we have noted previously).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that there is a physical reason for considering fluctuation probabilities in time and space. Previously, we noted that if one has a period= $\text{constant}/E$ and a wavelength = $\text{constant}/p$ associated with the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, then these shifts cancel and leave A unchanged. Thus A may be granular and linked with fluctuations in both space and time. We ultimately linked these to the quantum free particle $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. The question we address here is: Where is the physical reason for such fluctuations? We argue that a particle moving in a constant potential has constant energy and momentum. Thus on average it seems that nothing is happening, when in fact stochastic interactions may occur as a potential is physical and not a mathematical construct. Similarly a photon moving through a medium with index of refraction is described as moving smoothly with $p^2 = pn^2$ and $c^2 = c/n^2$ when in fact stochastic interactions create this smooth motion. Thus we argue that in order to solve the problem of one dimensional reflection/refraction, one must explicitly utilize a probability which describes the stochastic motion, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Balancing this and a momentum equation solves the problem, whereas a smooth nonstochastic picture does not.

We further argue that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ follow from the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to appropriate constraint. The product is: $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. In other words, the Lorentz invariant follows from maximization of Shannon's entropy considerations and is associated with stochasticity. Here we assume that for all frames moving with constant v , one must have $-E't' + p'x'$ being an invariant. We suggest that taking only the argument $-Et + px$ as an invariant, writing $v = x/t$ and ignoring the stochasticity is an approximation which yields a deterministic result. In particular, one may find the transformation from one frame to another moving at constant v and then express E and p in terms of m_0 and v . There also exists the invariant $-EE + pp = m_0m_0$ ($c=1$) which when expressed in terms of m_0 and v , yields an equation for $v(x)$ (i.e. based on energy conservation). One thus has deterministic classical mechanics follow from considerations of the argument of the probability arising from the maximization of two Shannon's entropies. We thus suggest that classical deterministic mechanics is a subset of the full probabilistic picture (i.e. quantum mechanics).

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein Gordon Equation, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)